

Guidance Document

Building New Plugins

This document offers some support for creating new plugins for DesignSpace, which can be used to replicate or employ the reactive links features. Additional support can be provided per request, after contacting the authors of the research paper “Using Reactive Links to Propagate Changes Across Engineering Models” at the following email addresses:

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1. Setup required

The jar files provided were compiled using Java 1.8 and will likely require this same Java version to run. Additionally, the server runs on the 8080 port, so this port has to be open for the server to start.

We have only tested the executables in a setup with a Windows OS. For any struggles on running the components, please contact the authors for support.

More support on creating the links and the usage of the tool can be seen in the demonstration videos linked in the original paper. We do not have the rights to share the data used during the evaluation or any of the other plugins used.

2. The components of the replication package

The replication package contains three .jar files that are archived together. These three jar files are as follows:

- main-4.0.jar – the DesignSpace server
- value-linking-4.0-jar-with-dependencies.jar – the DesignSpace SDK
- RequirementsManagementTool-1.0-SNAPSHOT-jar-with-dependencies.jar – the Requirements Tool, not needed for this replication

The Requirements Tool is a plugin created using the guidelines described below. We unfortunately cannot make the code available. The tool can be used in parallel with any other plugins created, or by itself. More details on this can be found in the Requirements Tool Guidelines Document.

3. Starting the DesignSpace server

All the communication between artifacts happens on the DesignSpace server. As such, this server has to be running at all times for the Requirements Tool to be used. If the server crashes, both the server and the tool have to be restarted.

The DesignSpace server can be started by running the jar file main-4.0.jar. We recommend using the command line, so that the server can be stopped at the end. In order to run the server, one has to execute the command:

```
java -jar main-4.0.jar
```

This command will initialize the server. Please wait until the server is fully started, marked by the line “Successfully initialized!”.

4. General considerations for a plugin

The DesignSpace plugins are designed based on the design goals presented in [1]. The main aims of these plugins is bidirectional communication with the DesignSpace server, as well as with the tool the plugin enhances, and consistency of information.

To make this possible, DesignSpace uses GRPC communication to transport information from the tool, through the SDK, to the server and back. The GRPC communication is already included in the DesignSpace SDK and can be used through the DesignSpace services (which will be discussed in further detail below).

The DesignSpace server and SDK use, as mentioned previously, Java 1.8. Additionally, the GUI components available in the SDK are created using Eclipse SWT 4.6.1. Please consider the limitations of both for the implementation of the plugin. If they present an issue for your experimental setup, please contact the authors of the paper, as newer or older versions of DesignSpace may have different configurations. It must be noted, however, that other versions of DesignSpace may have variations in the implementation of the reactive links.

The SDK provided is created for Java-based plugins. If needed, a C# SDK may also be available per request. While the linking implementation is mainly set on the server side, the C# SDK may have some slight differences in features and interface presentation.

5. The DesignSpace meta-metamodel

In order to provide the full extent of the collaborative and multi-tool features it proposes, DesignSpace acts as a common storage environment with a unified data representation. The goal of the plugins is to bridge the gap between this unified representation and the in-tool data representation. As such, the starting point for the development of a plugin is to decide how the data is to be translated into the DesignSpace meta-metamodel.

This meta-metamodel contains the following types:

- InstanceType – describes the structure of the artifacts, including what properties they may have, the structure of these properties (PropertyTypes) and any inheritance information from other InstanceTypes.
- PropertyType – describe the structure of a property: its name, the data type stored in the property, the cardinality of this property
- Instance – represents one artifact, of a selected InstanceType, and stores the actual information of this artifact in the properties modelled by the PropertyTypes

- Property – stores one piece of information about the artifact, such as the name. A property is uniquely associated with an instance, and each instance can have multiple properties storing the specific characteristics of the artifact.

The characteristics of a property:

- The name of the property is a string set in the PropertyType. Each instance of an InstanceType will then have this property.
- The data type stored can be a reference type (i.e. another InstanceType), or a base type: String, Integer/Long, Float/Double, Date and Boolean. After defining the PropertyType, one cannot assign a value of a different data type to any of the corresponding properties.
- The cardinality represents the number of data points (of the type specified by the data type above) that can be stored in the property. This can be:
 - Cardinality.SINGLE – only one data point can be stored (e.g. name = “Requirement”)
 - Cardinality.SET – a (Java) set of data points can be stored (e.g. in component, requirements is a Set property storing all the corresponding requirements)
 - Cardinality.LIST – a (Java) list of data points can be stored
 - Cardinality.MAP – a (Java) map of data points can be stored.

DesignSpace organizes the data stored on the server in workspaces. A workspace is a self-contained environment where a user can store and modify their artifacts without intruding on the work of another user. The collaboration between users is not discussed here but can be discussed further by request.

Everything that happens in DesignSpace happens in a workspace. The workspaces are created in a hierarchical structure, with the top-most accessible parent being the DesignSpace.PUBLIC_WORKSPACE. We advise against using this workspace as your main, but it can be used to set up information that should be available to all workspaces. A new workspace can be created at the time of connection or using the method:

```
DesignSpace.createWorkspace( name, (optionally) parent, user, tool, autocommit flag,
autoupdate flag )
```

Further, DesignSpace allows the organization of data within its server in different folders. These can be created by hand during the connection process or in code using the method:

```
DesignSpace.createFolder( workspace, parentFolderId, name)
```

By default, we encourage the use of the folder typesFolder for storing InstanceTypes and projectFolder for storing Instances (both folders are selected at the time of connection).

We recommend that the structure of the data is captured in InstanceTypes and PropertyTypes at the start of the plugin run, and then the artifacts from the tools can be captured in Instances with Properties as they are created or modified. However, InstanceTypes and PropertyTypes can also be created on the fly during the runtime.

In special cases, it may be the case that only one Instance of an InstanceType has a particular Property. An example is in the Requirements Tool if one requirement specifies a value that is only

part of this specific requirement. In these cases, a Property can be created on the fly for only this Instance. We discourage this practice in general, and encourage the creation of a PropertyType at the InstanceType level.

One more important aspect is the concept of transactions. The changes that happen in DesignSpace are grouped together in transactions, that should be concluded once the change is complete. This is done using the method `workspace.concludeTransaction()`. After concluding, the changes are sent to the DesignSpace server and to the services within it, specifically in this case, the reactive linking service.

On the SDK side, we can also create a `WorkspaceListener`. This is attached to the workspace and performs the specified operations every time a change occurs in the workspace. As such, it can react not only to the changes the user performs, but also to the feedback from the server and to changes performed by other users. This listener is required to update the in-tool information with the changes coming from the DesignSpace server.

6. The GUI components available

As part of the DesignSpace SDK, we are including the gui module which contains some SWT-based GUI components. These components include:

- `ConnectToWorkspaceDialog` – the connection dialog which should be started when the plugin is run
- `ElementDetailsWindow` – a view of the properties and property values for an Instance
- `NewFolderDialog` – a dialog for creating a new folder
- `Types and Instances viewers` which group the `InstanceTypes` or `Instances` on name or folder

Additionally, the value-linking (reactive linking) jar file also adds two dialogs specific to the links. One of these allows viewing the list of existing links, and the other allows the creation of new links.

7. Connecting to DesignSpace and using the GUI components

In order to connect to DesignSpace, the plugin must first select a workspace. The most simple way to do this is to use the `ConnectToWorkspaceDialog` mentioned above. In SWT, this can be done following these steps:

- Create a `Display` (`org.eclipse.swt.widgets.Display`) and `Shell(display)`. This will be the container and window showing the dialog
- Create a new instance of the `ConnectToWorkspaceDialog`
- When the user clicks the Connect button, the dialog will return the `Window.OK` signal
- At this point, one can retrieve the workspace and folder information from the dialog
- Once this information is available, one can create the instance types and start the plugin
- Please make sure to not allow the display to close during the run (using `display.sleep()`) and to dispose of it at the end. It may not be disposed of automatically in all cases.

The general pattern of this operation should be the following:

```
public static void main(String[] args) throws ExecutionException {  
    Display display = new Display();
```

```
Shell shell = new Shell(display);

ConnectToWorkspaceDialog dialog = new ConnectToWorkspaceDialog(shell, *tool name*, *tool
version*);
dialog.create();

if (dialog.open() == Window.OK) {
    Workspace workspace = dialog.getSelectedWorkspace();
    User user = dialog.getSelectedUser();
    Folder instancesFolder = dialog.getSelectedInstancesFolder();
    Folder typesFolder = dialog.getSelectedTypesFolder();

    *create the instance types or any mock data needed, run your plugin specific actions*

    while (!shell.isDisposed()) {
        if (!display.readAndDispatch()) display.sleep();
    }
    display.dispose();
}
}
```

References:

1. Sun C, Xia S, Sun D, Chen D, Shen H, Cai W (2006) Transparent adaptation of single-user applications for multi-user real-time collaboration. ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI) 13(4):531–582.